

Evaluation

Observation Protocol (to be filled out individually by the instructors after the workshop)

1. To what extent do the children understand what AI is and what ethical implications are associated with it?
2. Do the children show curiosity and motivation when using AI tools?
3. Were the children able to make connections between emotions and music?
4. Were the teaching methods sufficient to enable the children to acquire the target knowledge, skills, and attitudes?
5. Was the content appropriate for the target group?
6. Was the time distributed appropriately?
7. Was the work distributed fairly among the different children?
8. Was the level of difficulty of the technical requirements appropriate for the children?

The following questionnaire is to be filled out by the children

What do you think about the Workshop?

General

What was especially good?

And bad?

What was easy?

And difficult?

Did you understand the tasks?

Would you have liked more time?

About Artificial Intelligence

How would you define AI?

Do you think AI is beneficial in any way?

Could you give some examples of how AI might help people?

Do you think there are risks associated with using AI?

Could you give some examples of how AI might be dangerous to humans?

About the audiovisual Fairy-Tale

Do you think music was important in creating the digital fairy tale and why?

What was easy?

Creating suitable music Creating suitable images Same

Why?

What was more interesting?

Creating suitable music Creating suitable images Same

Why?

About digital competences

Have you ever heard of AI before the workshop?

How confident do you feel using computer tools like the ones used today?

Very confident Confident Not so confident Absolutely not confident

Why?

Did this workshop help you feel more confident?

Yes To some extent No

Why?

Do you want to experiment further with AI?

Free place for your thoughts

Thank you for coming